

RHETORICAL SENTENCES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES THROUGH THE PRISM OF THEIR MORPHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES

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ABSTRACT

The problem of researching rhetoric in dialogue and its morphological peculiarities in the English and Uzbek languages is considered in the given article

Introduction

At the present stage of development of linguistic sciences, when the problems of language as a form and environment of human communicative activity remain in the focus of attention of scientists, a comparative study of rhetoric in dialogue and morphological features in English and Uzbek languages allows us to systematize some linguistic phenomena. In view of this, the present study is of undeniable relevance. The study of the features of one of the eastern languages - Uzbek - and one of the European languages - English - is dictated by a number of reasons. Firstly, Uzbekistan and the UK are in a relationship of long-term intercultural dialogue, which contributed to the establishment of interethnic contacts in various fields: diplomacy, art, literature, etc. Secondly, the

history of the development of these societies allows us to say that they have both common features, and ethnographic identity in the economic, political, demographic and other spheres. Thirdly, from a linguistic point of view, the Uzbek and English languages are different types: agglutinative and analytical, which causes differences in their structure. Appeal to the materials of two linguocultures allows us to study the national and cultural features of the speech behavior of the speakers of these languages and to identify common and different features of morphology in dialogic speech acts in these languages.

Main part

The study of rhetoric in dialogue and its morphological features in the English and Uzbek languages is one of the underdeveloped problems in modern

linguistics, and so far no detailed coverage of the morphological features of this field has been done based on an analysis of their comparative-typological aspect. Language is the most important means of human communication, it is an instrument of thought and culture. The ancient Greek teacher of eloquence George said: "The word is a great ruler, who, having a very small and inconspicuous body, performs wonderful deeds. For it can drive away fear, and destroy sadness, and inspire joy, and awaken compassion..."

The power of persuasion, which is inherent in the word, shapes the soul as it wants." In recent years, rhetoric - the science of eloquence, the skill of speech, which for many centuries was a compulsory subject of school education, and then forgotten for a long time - has again become one of the most relevant and sought-after academic disciplines. This is due to the society's awareness of the need to improve and improve their speech culture, one of the components of which is speech skills. Rhetoric is the art of persuasion, influencing other people by means of mastery of speech and perfection of form, it is the art of speaking well in order to achieve the goals of communication, understanding and, from the standpoint of aesthetics, decorating speech for aesthetic purposes. One who has this art of speaking is a rhetorician. A rhetor is a person worthy and wishing good to his neighbor with his speech, appearance and image, striving for the common good with the help of his teachings. Knowledge of rhetorical rules and long-term exercises will help to master the skill of speech, win the attention and trust of the audience, and ensure success.

The power of the word increases in the conditions of study, training, careful preparation and practice of oral and written presentations. Rhetoric exists in such areas of speech action as philology, politics, jurisprudence, sociology, philosophy, psychology, logic, and so on. Rhetoric includes the rules of speech etiquette, the rules for the execution of documents, the rules for introducing monologue and dialogic speech, discussions, and polemics. Rhetoric exists in both monologues and dialogues. Dialogue is the object of study of rhetoric. Dialogue, as you know, is an oral conversation between two or more people. In dialogues, in order to influence his listener, the rhetorician, first of all, needs to know what he needs to increase or humiliate in his speech, what to say swiftly or funny or important; lush or thin; stately or polite; and then judge with what figures, with what thoughts, to what extent and in what disposition, he can achieve his intention. In order to convince and influence the listener, various linguistic techniques are used. These techniques have their own phonetic, morphological, lexical, syntactic and stylistic features.

According to O. Muminov, there are 171 suffixes in the Uzbek language, in English - Considering that English is an analytical language, and the Uzbek language is included in the group of agglutinative languages, we can conclude that in the Uzbek language this part of the word - suffixes - are used more often than in English. Our studies have shown that in the Uzbek language the suffix of the second person plural -siz, the suffix of the general question -mi, the suffix of the negative meaning -may, the suffix -chi make speech

more polite and help the rhetor to influence his listener ("Oynani ochib yuborolmay + siz + mi? "Ayting-chi, biz bilan bora olasizmi?... In English, in interrogative sentences, instead of suffixes, the particle not and the modal verbs can, will, could, standing before the subject ("Can you open the window, please? From the point of view of etiquette, the rhetor, addressing his listener by name, adds suffixes -jon (Botir + jon, Fattoh + jon), -xon (Saida + xon, Lobar + xon), -bek (Odil + bek, Rustam + bek) to the name and other related words aka (aka + jon), opa (opa + jon), uka (uka + jon), suffixes of the first person of the number (Botir + jon uka + m, Sayyora + xon. These suffixes make speech more polite and respectful. Unlike the Uzbek language, the words sir, Mr. , madam, etc., some of which are used before proper names as an application (Mr. Brown, Mrs. Smith), words of related meaning are not used. Instead of suffixes of the first person singular. numbers, it is customary to add the possessive pronoun of the first person of the number (my dear, my friend). Morphological studies have shown that in order to make their speech more convincing and expressive, the speaker uses utterances in: Umid qilaman siz kelasiz" b) incentive sentences ("Let's do it together" / "Ijizat bering, life raqsga taklif qilsam" c) conditional clauses ("If you don't mind, open the window" , "If you would not mind, we will play computer" , "If it is not difficult for you" / "Agar qiyin bo'lmasa, ushbu sumkani uzatib yuboring", "Agar malol kelmasa, biz bilan birga borsangiz" d) exclamatory sentences. In such sentences, in order to influence his listener, the rhetor usually praises or talks about his good qualities. ("Dear, you look

Do you mind dancing with me?" / "Azizim, buncha go'zalsiz!", "Keling raqs tushamiz d) interrogative sentences ("Can you help me?", "Close the door, will you", "Let's discuss this question, shall we?" / "Bugun kinoga borishga nima deysiz?", "Menga yordamlashib yuboring desam hafa bo'lmaysizmi?. According to Joy Ayres and Janice Miller, in English, to get any information faster, interrogative questions are usually used sentences such as: "Could you please?", "Would you please" Studies have shown that in the studied languages, interrogative sentences have more persuasive power than incentive sentences. For example, if we compare two sentences in the studied languages: "Open the window" " Oynani oching" and "Will / can you open the" / "Oynani ochib yuborolmaysizmi?" then in these languages the second sentence is pronounced more politely.

Conclusion

Thus, politeness is a very important tool of a rhetorician. Our research data also showed that words and expressions that refer to the following parts of speech: a) noun (thanks, dears, / jonim, iltimos, rahmat); b) adjective (dear, respectful / azizim, hurmatli); c) verb (to welcome, will you, could you, I hope / ijizat etsangiz, kechirasiz, aytolmaysizmi); d) adverbial phrase with a noun (with pleasure / jonim bilan, bajonidil); e) the numeral "one", which in English is often expressed by the article (just a moment, please / bir daqiqa vaqtingizni olsam e) pronoun (thank you, can you, excuse me / siz borasiz deb o'ylaymiz, biz ishonamiz); The pronoun II person singular sen in the Uzbek language denotes some impoliteness on the part of the rhetor when addressing his listener,

therefore this part of speech is often not used when. languages serves as an expression of respect for the interlocutor⁴. In English, the personal pronoun of the second person singular (you) is homonymous with the form of the second person plural, so the pragmatics of politeness in this case is neutralized. Thus, the English language is deprived of this means of expression. Taking into account the above, it should be noted that the rhetoric in dialogues in English and Uzbek has its own national and general morphological features. In the Uzbek language, suffixes are more often used to convince the listener, and in English, modal

verbs in interrogative sentences and possessive pronouns are used. All kinds of sentences in both studied languages make speech more persuasive, and interrogative sentences have more persuasive power than incentive ones. Studies taking into account parts of speech show that in the languages under consideration, the rhetor uses rhetorical words and expressions related to all parts of speech, but in English the numeral one is replaced by the indefinite article a with the meaning - one. So, the etiquette forms of politeness in the Uzbek and English languages have both similarities and differences.

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